

A STUDY ON THE CHANGING SENARIO OF NEW TAX REGIME IN INDIA

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Abstract

Section 115BAC of the Income Tax Act refers to this new tax structure as the Alternate Tax structure. Given the alternative tax stabs for the Indian tax payers. The present study was done with the object of study the features of New Tax regime in India and to analyse the tax benefits and tax slabs of New Tax regime in India. The study was based on secondary data collected through research papers and websites. The study analyse the tax stabs and taxable amount from 2020-21 to 2025-26. The results shows that the tax payer got the tax benefits of Rs157500 during the financial year 2025-26 as compare to financial 2021-22 and last 5 years the tax payer's benefits are increased continuously under New tax regime and it benefits medial class people in India. They have more money for spending and also increase the economic activity at large.

INTRODUCTION

Nirmala Sitharaman, the finance minister, introduced a new tax structure in the Union Budget 2020. Income Tax Act 1961 (India, 2020) Section 115BAC of the Income Tax Act refers to this new tax structure as the Alternate Tax structure. There are six rates available: 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%. Three of these rates are exempt under the current tax structure. The main characteristic of the new or alternative tax regime is that, in contrast to the previous one, it has more slabs with lower tax rates.

Section 115 BAC Budget 2023 states that a salaried individual may choose to use the Old Tax Regime, with the New Tax Regime remaining the default choice when the return is being filled out. However, they can only opt out of the New Tax Regime once in their lifetime and only if they do not earn company income. There are some exemptions and deductions that the taxpayer must give up in order to choose the New Tax Regime.

TAX STAB FROM FY 2020-21 TO FY 2025-26 UNDER NEW TAX REGIME

Tax Stab for FY 2020-21	Tax Rate	Tax Stab for FY 2023-24	Tax Rate	Tax Stab for FY 2024-25	Tax Rate	Tax Stab for FY 2025-26	Tax Rate
Up to ₹.2.5 lakh	NIL	Up to ₹3 lakh	NIL	Up to ₹.3 lakh	NIL	Up to ₹.4 lakh	NIL
₹2.5 lakh-₹5 lakh	5%	₹3 lakh- ₹6 lakh	5%	₹3 lakh-₹7 lakh	5%	₹4 lakh- ₹8 lakh	5%
₹5 lakh-₹7.5 lakh	10%	₹6 lakh-₹9 lakh	10%	₹7 lakh-₹10 lakh	10%	₹8 lakh-₹12 lakh	10%
₹7.5 lakh- ₹10 lakh	15%	₹9 lakh-₹12 lakh	15%	₹10 lakh-₹12 lakh	15%	₹12 lakh-₹16 lakh	15%
₹10 lakh- ₹12.5 lakh	20%	₹12 lakh-₹15 lakh	20%	₹12 lakh-₹15 lakh	20%	₹16 lakh-₹20 lakh	20%
₹12.5 lakh- ₹15 lakh	25%	More than ₹15 lakh	30%	More than ₹15 lakh	30%	₹20 lakh - ₹24 lakh	25%
More than ₹15 lakh	30%	NA	NIL	NA	NIL	More than ₹24 lakh	30%

THE EXEMPTIONS AND DEDUCTIONS AVAILABLE UNDER THE NEW REGIME

Under the New tax regime, you can claim tax exemption for the following:

- Transport allowances in case of a specially-Abled person.
- Conveyance allowance received to meet the conveyance expenditure incurred as part of the employment.
- Any compensation received to meet the cost of travel on tour or transfer.
- Daily allowance received to meet the ordinary regular charges or expenditure you incur on account of absence from his regular place of duty.
- Perquisites for official purposes
- Exemption on voluntary retirement 10(10C), gratuity u/s 10(10) and Leave encashment u/s 10(10AA)
- Interest on Home Loan on let-out property (Section 24)

- Gifts up to Rs 50,000
- Deduction for employer's contribution to NPS account [Section 80CCD(2)]
- Deduction for additional employee cost (Section 80JJA)
- Budget 2023 introduced a standard deduction of Rs 50,000 under New Tax Regime applicable from FY 2023-24. This has been increased to Rs.75,000 in Budget 2024 applicable from FY 2024-25
- Budget 2023 also introduced deduction under Section 57(ia) of family pension income
- Budget 2023 further introduced deduction of amount paid or deposited in the Agniveer Corpus Fund under Section 80CCH(2)
- In Budget 2024 Limit of maximum Deduction under Family Pension has been increased from Rs. 15,000 to Rs. 25,000.
- The deduction on employers contribution to pension Scheme as per Section 80CCD (2) has been increased from 10% of salary to the 14% of salary in Budget 2024.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In their study, Tejaswini Shevate and Smita Pande (2023) analyze individual taxpayers' preferences and their awareness of the two-tax system, assisting them in making informed decisions about their tax regime selection. In their study on tax planning strategies used by the salaried class, Purva Savaliya and Vivek Ayre (2023) wanted to find out how much the salaried class knew about these approaches. In this study, Renuka Ekanath Walunj (2021) investigates the tax planning awareness of salaried employees. The findings indicate that employees lack knowledge regarding both short-term and long-term capital gains, and those individuals should adopt new tax planning strategies instead of sticking with traditional ones in order to improve market returns. David Joseph and Sumesh G S (2020) collect responses from salaried employees in Kottayam taluk in an effort to gauge their level of awareness and perception regarding tax planning schemes.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To study the features of New Tax regime in India
- To analyse the tax benefits of New Tax regime in India
- To study the tax slabs of New Tax regime

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Study is based on Secondary data. It was collected from published research papers, Finance Bills, amendments made in the Income tax Act 1961 and different Websites.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 : Tax Stab and Calculation of Tax Amount from FY 2020-21 to FY 2025-26 under New Tax Regime (Tax Calculation for 25 Lakh Income)

Tax Stab for FY 2020-21	Tax Rate	Tax Amt	Tax Stab for FY 2023-24	Tax Rate	Tax Amt	Tax Stab for FY 2024-25	Tax Rate	Tax Amt	Tax Stab for FY 2025-26	Tax Rate	Tax Amt
Up to ₹.2.5 lakh	NIL	0	Up to ₹3 lakh	NIL	0	Up to ₹.3 lakh	NIL	0	Up to ₹.4 lakh	NIL	0
₹2.5 lakh- ₹5 lakh	5%	12500	₹3 lakh- ₹6 lakh	5%	15000	₹3 lakh- ₹7 lakh	5%	20000	₹4 lakh- ₹8 lakh	5%	20000
₹5 lakh- ₹7.5 lakh	10%	25000	₹6 lakh- ₹9 lakh	10%	30000	₹7 lakh- ₹10 lakh	10%	30000	₹8 lakh- ₹12 lakh	10%	40000
₹7.5 lakh- ₹10 lakh	15%	37500	₹9 lakh- ₹12 lakh	15%	45000	₹10 lakh- ₹12 lakh	15%	30000	₹12 lakh- ₹16 lakh	15%	60000
₹10 lakh- ₹12.5 lakh	20%	50000	₹12 lakh- ₹15 lakh	20%	60000	₹12 lakh- ₹15 lakh	20%	60000	₹16 lakh- ₹20 lakh	20%	80000

₹12.5 lakh-	25	6250	More than ₹ 15 lakh	30	3000	More than ₹ 15 lakh	30	3000	₹20 lakh - ₹24 lakh	25	1000
₹15 lakh	%	0		%	00		%	00		%	00
More than ₹ 15 lakh	30	3000	NA	NIL		NA	NIL		More than ₹ 24 lakh	30	3000
	%	00								%	0
Total Tax		4875			4500			4400			3300
		00			00			00			00

Source: Calculated amounts

The table 1 reveals that the Tax Stab and Calculation of Tax Amount from FY 2020-21 to FY 2025-26 under New Tax Regime for Rs. 25 lakhs income taxpayers. New tax regime was introduced as a alternative tax option for old tax structure in the financial year 2020-21. There are six rates available: 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%. The tax stab amount was various from year to year and tax payers also get different benefits. In the financial year 2020-21 tax stab was nil upto Rs2.5 lakhs and it was increased to Rs 4 lakhs in the year 2025-26. In the financial year 2020-21 tax stab was 5 % for Rs2.5 lakhs to Rs 5 lakhs income with the tax amount of Rs 12500 and it was increased to Rs 4 lakhs to Rs 8 lakhs income with the tax amount of Rs.20000. It benefits to the tax payers to pay Rs 27500 less amount for Rs 8 lakh amount of income in the year 2025-26. In the financial year 2020-21 tax stab was 10 % for Rs5 lakhs to Rs 7.5 lakhs income with the tax amount of Rs 25000 and it was increased to Rs 8 lakhs to Rs 12 lakhs income with the tax amount of Rs.40000. It benefits to the tax payers to pay Rs 55000 less amount for Rs 12 lakh amount of income in the year 2025-26. In the financial year 2020-21 tax stab was 15 % for Rs7.5 lakhs to Rs 10 lakhs income with the tax amount of Rs 37500 and it was increased to Rs 12 lakhs to Rs 16 lakhs income with the tax amount of Rs.60000. It benefits to the tax payers to pay Rs 97500 less amount for Rs 16 lakh amount of income in the year 2025-26. In the financial year 2020-21 tax stab was 20 % for Rs10 lakhs to Rs 12.5 lakhs income with the tax amount of Rs 50000 and it was increased to Rs 16 lakhs to Rs 20 lakhs income with the tax amount of Rs.80000. It benefits to the tax payers to pay Rs 137500 less amount for Rs 20 lakh amount of income in the year 2025-26. In the financial year 2020-21 tax stab was 25 % for Rs12.5 lakhs to Rs 15 lakhs income with the tax amount of Rs 62500 and it was increased to Rs 20 lakhs to Rs 24 lakhs income with the tax amount of

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Rs.100000. It benefits to the tax payers to pay Rs 127500 less amount for Rs 24 lakh amount of income in the year 2025-26. It shows that in last 5 years tax payers benefits are increased continuously under New tax regime and it benefits medial class people in India have more money for spending and also increases the economic activity at large.

Figure 1: Tax Amount and Tax Benefits for 25 lakhs income Tax payers under New Tax Regime

Source: Calculated amounts

The above figure shows the tax benefits gained by tax payer compare to 2021-22 tax amount. Total of Rs 487500 tax amount was paid by tax payer for Rs 25 lakhs of income during the financial year 2021-22. It was reduced to Rs 450000 and got tax benefits of Rs.37500 during the financial year 2023-24. In the year 2024-25 it was reduced to Rs 440000 and with the tax benefit of Rs.47500 and it future reduced to Rs 330000 with the tax benefit of Rs157500 during the financial year 2025-26 as compare to financial 2021-22.

CONCLUSION

A new tax structure in the Union Budget 2020, Income Tax Act 1961 (India, 2020) Section 115BAC of the Income Tax Act refers to this new tax structure as the Alternate Tax structure. Given the alternative tax stabs for the Indian tax payers. The present study analyse the tax stabs and taxable amount from 2020-21 to 2025-26. The results shows that the tax payer got the tax benefits of Rs157500 during the financial year 2025-26 as compare to financial 2021-22 and last 5 years tax payers benefits are increased continuously under New tax regime and it benefits medial class people in India. They have more money for spending and also increase the economic activity at large.

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